

Hyperspectral Data Compression using High-Performance Embedded Space Computing

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1 INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the enhancement of a data compression computing system that operates on imaging spectrometer data. The implementation is part of the focal plane interface electronics-digital (FPIE-D) and includes AMD System-on-Chip (SoC) Zynq-based and KU060-based versions. JPL imaging spectrometers can acquire data with 640, 1280, or 3000 cross-track positions with 328 or 480 bands at up to 216 images per second. Uses for imaging spectrometer data include studying the mineral dust cycle, methane detection, analysis of biodiversity, and fire detection.

We have implemented the data compression system on an AMD Zynq-based space-qualified custom FPIE-D SoC commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) Alpha Data 7z1 hardware, which fits into a 120mm by 190mm by 40mm assembly that uses 9 watts at peak performance. The computing element is a Xilinx Zynq Z7045Q SoC, which includes a Kintex-7 FPGA and two ARM Cortex-A9 processors. We have also implemented the data compression system on the AMD KU060-based FPIE-D FPGA COTS Alpha Data KU1 hardware PCIe board.

The changes to the Fast Lossless Extended (FLEX) data compression block (a modified implementation of the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard) compared to the implementation used for the Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation (EMIT) mission were: (1) Band Interleaved by Line (BIL) scan order (instead of Band Interleaved by Pixel (BIP)), (2) narrow local sums, (3) a modification to use 'stale' prediction weights, (4) a minor modification to the predictor, and (5) a pipelined predictor-quantizer core that was made possible by the other changes. These changes together do not adversely affect the achieved compression ratio. The motivation for the 'stale weights' was that with BIL scan order and narrow local sums, the main obstacle to pipelining the prediction calculation in an FPGA implementation is that the weight update calculation requires the sign of the prediction error for the previous sample. By using weights that are a few samples old, it is possible to pipeline the prediction calculation.

The enhancement provides an increase in data throughput by a factor of 2.5 compared to the EMIT implementation. Specifically, the FPIE-D SoC 7z1 achieves a data throughput of 60 MSamples/sec (compared to 25 MSamples/sec for EMIT), allowing real-time data compression for a JPL imaging spectrometer similar to EMIT (40 MSamples/sec), using a 3 FLEX BIL core implementation. The FPIE-D FPGA KU1 board achieves a data throughput of 218 MSamples/sec using an 11 FLEX BIL core implementation, which is the maximum number of cores based on the resources available on the KU060.

The FPGA implementation was stress-tested on the FPIE-D FPGA KU1 board using different image patterns, image sizes (number of cross-tracks from 32 to 1280 in increments of 32, and number of bands from 32 to 480 in increments of 8), and compression fidelity parameters (maximum error values varying by band and randomly ranging from 0 (lossless) to 1023). Over 20 million images of different sizes, totaling 23 terabytes (TB) of data, were tested. We also demonstrated using Alpha Data performance analysis FPGA IPs, that the limited PCIe data bandwidth (1.4 GBytes/sec) does not affect the compression data throughput, allowing the host processors to perform real-time acquisition and downlink while the FPGA simultaneously performs real-time data compression. Finally, we stress-tested a 1-core implementation on the FPIE-D SoC 7z1 board and verified the functional test on a 3-core implementation.

2 FLEX BIP DEPLOYED FOR EMIT MISSION

EMIT is looking at the mineral dust cycle which has multiple impacts to the Earth System [1][2][3][10]. The surface mineral dust lifted by winds into the atmosphere is the major component of atmospheric aerosols (Fig. 2). The surface mineral dust sources are located in arid dust regions of the world (Fig. 1). The science objective of EMIT is to close the gap in our understanding of mineral dust heating and cooling impact on the Earth now and in the future [10] by

determining the surface mineralogy of mineral dust sources. EMIT images have 1280 cross track samples (spanning 60 km on the ground) and 328 spectral samples, each viewing a distinct, narrow part of the electromagnetic spectrum (ranging from 380 nm to 2500 nm). For EMIT one three-dimensional image (or “frame”) includes 32 spatially coadded slices in the along-track direction, yielding an image size of 26.8 Mbytes. Spacecraft that acquire spectral images that include hundreds of bands may have modest bandwidths available to transfer the data to the ground [3]; for EMIT the data bandwidth is an average of 7.4 Mbits/sec [11], and there is much interest in processing and compressing the data efficiently [4][5][6] before transmission. The data compression implemented for EMIT uses 3 FLEX BIP cores with a combined maximum data throughput of 24 MSamples/sec [15][22][23].

Figure 1. Arid Dust Source Regions

Figure 2. Mineral Dust Source Emission

Figure 3. File Size Histogram of cloud screened and compressed data

Figure 4. EMIT Coverage and Greenhouse Gases Detection from August 10, 2022 to December 11, 2023 (blue squares made of 1280 cross-track by 1280 along track co-added pixels).

From August 13, 2022 to September 5 (22 days), the EMIT FPIE-D SoC acquired and processed over 200974 frames, which is a total of 10.8 TB of raw data (before co-adding). After co-adding, cloud screening and compression this corresponded to 1.4 TB of data, which has been downlinked, and this became a total of 4.2 TB of science data on the ground after decompression. The co-added frames acquired can be classified into 6 categories from a cloud screening and compression perspective: frames dropped due to being deemed cloudy (11.8% of the frames), dark acquisition over the ocean (average compression ratio of 5:1), science acquisition over water (compression ratio 4.4:1), science acquisition with no clouds (compression ratio 3.4:1), and science acquisition with clouds (compression of 2.8:1). (Compression ratios are for co-added images and based on the original stored size of 16 bits per sample). EMIT was launched with SpaceX ISS Commercial Resupply Service (CRS-25) using SpaceX Cargo Dragon 2 C208 S/C with Falcon 9 rocket, Tuesday July 14th, 2022. Fig. 4 shows the EMIT Coverage and Greenhouse gases detection from August 10, 2022 to December 11, 2023. The data is available on the EMIT Open Data portal: <https://earth.jpl.nasa.gov/emit/data/data-portal/coverage-and-forecasts/>.

3 FLEX ENHANCEMENTS

The changes to the JPL FLEX data compression firmware (a modified implementation of the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard) compared to the implementation used for the EMIT mission were: (1) BIL scan order, (2) narrow local sums, (3) a modification to use ‘stale’ prediction weights, (4) a minor modification to the predictor using the damping parameter to vary with y, and (5) a pipelined predictor-quantizer core that was made possible by the other changes. Our changes are

implemented by modifying existing blocks in our modular architecture for very fast development. FPGA implementations of CCSDS 123.0-B-2 [16][12] and enhancements to the standard have been proposed by multiple groups.

In [17], Sanchez et al. propose a mathematical model to reduce data dependencies in the feedback loop of CCSDS 123.0-B-2 predictor by removing completely the quantization stage from the feedback loop without any impact in the compression performance through an elaborate mathematical derivation. In [18], Valsesia et al. propose a method based on the prequantization of the image followed by a lossless predictive compressor to alleviate the data dependencies which constrain the achievable throughput; it is well known that prequantization incurs a rate-distortion cost but in [18] a neural network is used to recover this cost. In [19] Bascones et al. propose to use a novel sample ordering called frame interleaved by diagonal with a predictor stage that has been designed to work in this order, and two reorder buffers encapsulate it to be band interleaved by pixel (BIP) compliant. The method is able to process a sample per cycle at over 250MHz and use 50% of KU060 FPGA for image (512 bands by 4096 frames by 1024 cross-track). In [20], Chatziantoniou et al. introduce a high-throughput hardware implementation of the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 Hybrid Entropy Coder using a deep and elastic pipeline achieving 1 Sample/cycle which corresponds to a constant throughput performance of 305 MSample/sec on a KCU105 FPGA. Finally, in [21] Chatziantoniou et al. implement a technique that bypasses the throughput performance bottleneck of CCSDS 123.0-B-2 with an external, hardware-efficient pre-quantizer, allowing the predictor to operate in lossless mode and achieve 285 MSample/sec for a single core on a Kintex Ultrascale XCKY040.

3.1 FLEX BIL Core

The JPL FLEX BIL compression core Data Flow block diagram is shown in Fig. 5. The data flows between the 3 arithmetic modules implementing the core of the compressor [12][16]. The predictor quantizer block computes the mapped quantizer index $\delta_z(t)$. The weight update block calculates the weight vector for each sample. The entropy encoder block produces the compressed image data. The uncompressed, compressed, and intermediary data are provided by the internal memories and internal FIFOs which interface with the two external DDR3 memories. The predictor, the weight update and the entropy encoder blocks are pipelined: when the predictor is working on sample index $t+1$, the weight-update and the entropy encoder are working on the sample index t . The compression initialization data used by the weight update and the predictor quantizer block are programmable through serial command to the FPPIE-D.

Figure 5. FLEX BIL Compression core Data Flow Control Block Diagram

Going from FLEX BIP to FLEX BIL requires the firmware to now process samples along the cross track (x dimension) as opposed to processing data “down” a band (z dimension). This means the core will be receiving data in a different order when it’s read from memory. For example, FLEX BIL will first receive sample coordinate $y=0, z=0, x=0$ but the next sample will be from $y=0, z=0, x=1$ so we’re actually compressing a different sample sequence. This means we’re

going to present prediction differences to the encoder in a different order, resulting in a different compression output (not backward compatible).

In general, the algorithm between BIP and BIL the same, so the compute elements are similar, however now when the hardware needs a value from the previous band ($z-1$), that value is no longer the previous value that just came out of the dataflow/memory, the $z-1$ value for a given cross track was processed 1280 samples ago. As such, the storage and presentation of PREZ, Sample Representatives, and deltas for previous y,z,x positions must now be buffered differently. In some cases buffers were reduced as shown in the “flex_prez_mem.vhd” for Buffer PREZ along cross track, in other whole new BRAMs were added as shown in the “flex_dvector.vhd” for $d[p]$ vector.

The block “flex_data_control.vhd” on the top of Fig. 12 shows the logic block that drives the sample index information to all the other blocks letting them know the y,z,x coordinate of the sample that currently being started. The block diagrams “flex_init_control.vhd”, “flex_source_fifo.vhd”, “flex_prez_mem.vhd” and “flex_dvector.vhd” in Fig. 12 show the modules which buffer sample data and compression coefficients driven to the “Weight_Update.vhd” and “Predictor_quantizer.vhd” FPGA blocks. These memories required updates to store and select along the cross track (new order in which data arrives). For example, if the “Predictor_quantizer.vhd” FPGA block is working on the sample from $y=1, z=1, x=1$, it needs the $y=1, z=0, x=0$ (y_mx1_zm1) sample representative per the CCSDS. For FLEX BIL core, this sample was seen 1179 samples ago (1280 cross tracks – 1). That means, the FIFO must store 1280 sample representatives. The FLEX BIP core works in a similar fashion but only has to store a values for each band index (480).

3.2 Local Sum with Narrow Neighbour-Oriented

The “Local Sum with Wide Neighbor-oriented” of the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard allows to use the values that have been previously computed, so we don’t stall the pipeline implemented for the predictor quantizer FPGA module.

Fig. 6 shows a sample “zyx” near the middle of each diagram. From there, algorithm defines a different set of neighboring values that are used generate the predicted value.

Figure 6. Computation of sample representative $zm1_y_xm1$ for “Local Sum Narrow Neighbor-oriented” for FLEX BIL core

The diagram “Local Sum Wide Neighbor-oriented” in Fig. 6, shows that “zyx” sample is depended on the neighbor immediately to its left: “ z_y_xm1 ($y, z, x-1$)”. This works fine when processing using a FLEX BIP core because samples are being processed vertically “down” each column and the sample to the left was processed 480 samples ago assuming a 480-band spectral imager ($N_z=480$). If we tried to implement the “Local Sum with Wide Neighbor-oriented” with FLEX BIL core in firmware, the RTL would have to wait to process each sample until after its neighbor to left “ z_y_xm1 ” sample representative value is available which is 26 clock cycles in our implementation of the predictor_quantizer block. To break this dependency for FLEX BIL core, we implemented the “Local Sum Narrow Neighbor-oriented” algorithm and use buffers to make the “ $zm1_y_xm1$ ” neighbor available when processing “zyx”. In the FLEX BIL core case, “ $zm1_y_xm1$ ” came out of the predictor quantizer one cross track ago + 1 which corresponds to a buffer 1281 for our spectral imager with 1280 cross track samples ($N_x=1280$).

3.3 Pipeline of the Predictor Quantizer module

Let’s assume you have fast DMA engines between DDR memory and FPGA fabric and a “Predictor_quantizer” FPGA module that can encode samples as fast as it receives them. In this case, the number of clock cycles to process a raw sample then comes down to how fast the “Weight_Update” FPGA module can update the weights and get the data out of the “Predictor_quantizer” block. Since the “Predictor_quantizer” module does not have any immediate dependencies, we

can run multiple “Predictor_quantizer” FPGA module in parallel. In our implementation, the FLEX BIL core runs 3 instances of “Predictor_quantizer” FPGA module in parallel as shown in the Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Pipeline Implementation of FLEX BIL Predictor Quantizer running 3 instances of Predictor_quantizer.vhd in parallel

The “Weight_Update.vhd” FPGA module uses “STALE” coefficients that are from nearby previous samples ($x-6$). Given the current implementation of the “Weight_Update.vhd” FPGA module takes us 9 clock cycles to produce the updated weights (“W_p_z(vector)”) for the next “Predictor_quantizer” input plus one clock cycle to stage the data to the “Predictor_Quantizer” FPGA module, the “Weight_Update.vhd” FPGA module can only produce a new weight every 10 clock cycles to the “Predictor_quantizer” FPGA module. Since “Predictor_quantizer” takes 28 clock cycles per sample to generate encoded value, the sample representative and the dvector, the pipeline implementation of the “Predictor_quantizer” needs 3 “Predictor_quantizer” instances to keep up with a new “Weight_Update” producing a weight update every 10 clock cycles as shown in Fig. 7.

Faster data throughput may be possible with additional optimizations to the “Weight update” design, however the 10 clock cycles per sample data throughput of the “Weight update” is sufficient to compress images at 200MSamples per second on a KU60, keeping up with current spectral imager sample data rates.

3.4 Stale Weights of the Weight_update module

With BIL scan order and narrow local sums, the main obstacle to pipelining the prediction calculation in an FPGA implementation is that the weight update calculation requires the sign of the prediction error for the previous sample. By using the weights that are a few samples old, it is possible to do some pipelining of the prediction calculation. Note however that the use of such “stale weights” is not compliant with CCSDS-123.0-B-2.

In more detail, during compression the compressor dynamically adapts its prediction weights via a feedback mechanism. The “predictor quantizer” FPGA module adjusts the weights after each predicted value is quantized. Recall, we’re processing along the cross track (BIL scan order), and the weight for at cross track x needs to be updated from the result at cross track $x-1$. Since we don’t want to wait for the “predictor quantizer” FPGA module to finish the previous sample (that would require waiting 26 clock cycles in our FPGA implementation of the “predictor quantizer”), we instead use predictor quantizer from a few samples back, in our implementation 6 samples back. These are known as “STALE WEIGHT” selections. Using the “STALE_WEIGHT” allows the weights to be updated every 10 clock cycles, which is the pipeline depth of the Weight Update block. Since the weights are updated based on neighbouring differences, the differences are buffered inside “dvector” RAMS as shown in the left diagram of Fig. 8. And similarly, the right diagram in Fig. 8 alludes to other parameters such as “rho” must be buffered to provide the correct values for compression.

Figure 8. Stale Weight Implementation in the “Weight update.vhd” of the FLEX BIL core

3.5 Damping parameter ϕ_z to vary with y of the predictor-quantizer block

In some cases, a positive value of the sample representative damping parameter ϕ_z improves overall compression but has a significantly negative effect for small values of y . In the implementation of the FLEX BIL “Predictor-Quantizer” FPGA module, instead of using a constant value of the sample representative damping parameter ϕ_z , we used $\phi_z = 0$ when $y = 0$ and $\phi_z = 4$ when $y > 0$. The implementation of the FLEX BIP “Predictor-Quantizer” FPGA module uses $\phi_z = 3$ for all y . Note that having ϕ_z depend on the value of y is not compliant with CCSDS-123.0-B-2, but it is planned to include a provision for such dependence in Issue 3 of CCSDS-123.0.

3.6 Performance with Stale Weights and Damping Parameter ϕ_z varying with y

Fig. 9 shows the performance dependence on stale weight and damping parameters (with damping indicated by the value of $\phi_z/2^0$) for images from EMIT with 1280 cross-track sample ($N_x=1280$), 328 bands ($N_z=328$), 32 images per frame ($N_y=32$) and 14-bit samples. For wide column-oriented local sums, $\phi_z/2^0 = 3/8$ works reasonably well (call this the baseline, which includes reduced prediction mode and $P=3$). Changing to narrow column-oriented local sums, and keeping other parameters the same, results in a compressed size that is more than 10% larger, even though narrow column-oriented local sums are the same as wide column-oriented local sums when $y > 0$. The cause of this appears to be that for $y=0$, the predictions are bad enough to produce instability/oscillatory behavior in the sample representatives, and this propagates for several y values (there is still significant oscillation for $y > 3$). Setting $\phi_z = 0$ for $y=0$ and making no other changes produces a compressed size that is very close to the size achieved in the baseline case.

Figure 9. Performance dependence on stale weight and damping parameters for a set of EMIT images ($N_x=1280$, $N_y=32$, $N_z=328$, 14-bit samples)

4 ZYNQ BASED HARDWARE PLATFORM FOR SPACE

4.1 Spectral Imager with FPIE-D SoC avionics

The FPIE-D SoC Hardware is composed of 3 components (Fig. 10). The first component is a flight modification of COTS Alpha Data ADM-XRC-7Z1/XQ7Z045-2/CC1A Zynq SoC XMC Defense Grade [7][8][9][13]. The second component is an Alpha Data ADC-CUST-7Z1 Custom Carrier with buffer, connector, rad hard watch dog timer and space Oscillators. The third component is an Alpha Data Custom Chassis. The Zynq 7Z100 System on the chip has Dual ARM core Processor Subsystem from which we will only use one because we disable the L2 cache and a FPGA Programmable Logic Kintex-7 FPGA. The FPIE-D SoC has a volume: 190 by 120 by 30 mm, a weight of 1Kg and a power of 3Watt when running only the ARM and 9 Watt when running the FPGA and ARM. The hardware is compatible with LEO orbit (from 200 to 2000 km). JPL has tested COTS parts for destructive Latch-up and eliminate unused functionalities such as ETH, USB, micro-controller on the COTS board and integrated Rad Hard Parts such as oscillator, hardware reset to allow a watch dog timer functionality if required by the S/C bus. The FPIE-D SoC has memories which consist of a QSPI Flash for Booting (2 X 256Mbits) and a DDR3 SDRAM for PS (512 MBytes) and for PL (2 X 256 MBytes). The FPIE-D SoC interfaces include 146 LVDS for FPIE raw data, compressed data, and Full Camera Link (0.5Gbit/sec) for ground testing. It includes also SPI for communicating with Focal Plane Interface Electronics, ROIC, Heaters, Temperature and finally RS422 (Cmd & Tlm).

The functionalities of the FPIE-D SoC are multiple and the FPIE-D SoC play a central role in the control of the spectral imager (Fig. 11). The FPIE-D SoC programs frame rates of FPA CHROMA from 1 MSamples/sec corresponding to 3 lines/sec to 40 MSamples/sec corresponding to 128 lines/sec. The Nominal frame rate is 20 MSamples/sec which corresponds to 65 frames/sec. The FPIE-D SoC acquires 640X480 samples 16 bits (used 14 bits), detects Clouds and applies region of interest which remove bands and cross track sample without information because focal plane array detector is saturated. The FPIE-D SoC then compress Losslessly in real-time hyperspectral data with a compression ratio of up to 4:1 and transmits compressed data through LVDS for flight and through Camera Link for Diagnostic. The FPIE-D SoC is also responsible to provide housekeeping telemetry with instrument health (Temperature) and synchronization

time between PPS and frame. The FPIE-D SoC programs digital control of temperature control and focus motor mechanism and provides the capability of in-flight programming Software and Firmware with Multiple images to allow

Figure 10. Focal Plane Interface Electronics-Digital System-on-Chip (FPIE-D SoC) Avionics for spectral imager

Figure 11. Spectral imager with Focal Plane Array (FPA), Cryocooler, Focus motor, Thermal control and FPIE-D SoC avionics

fall back recovery. Finally, the FPIE-D SoC will communicate to the S/C through RS422 Command and telemetry and LVDS for science data

4.2 Software and Firmware Architecture

The flight software runs on just one of the two Zynq ARM cores, with L1 caches and L2 cache disabled for SEU mitigation. The other core is unused. The architecture of the FPIE-D SoC portion of the software has 3 layers (Fig. 13):

Figure 12. FPIE-D SoC Zynq-7000 hardware architecture, and

Figure 13. FPIE-D SoC Application Flight software architecture

Application FSW High level which let separate the mission specific code from control of the hardware, the Hardware Abstraction layer which let us switch operating systems of target board and driver and OS Layer which separate the kernel code from application code. The hardware layer is implemented in the FPGA and on the board. The separation of layers allows the development effort to be distributed while allowing the designs to be easily re-targeted to existing or new modules. The FPGA design is divided into many sub-modules, each concerned with a single task typically controlled by registers accessed by software running on the ARM core(s) (Fig. 12). The “data flows” in the firmware (FW) design are steered by software (SW) via control registers. Interrupts are used from the Zynq PL to signal software threads (running on the Zynq PS) when operations complete or when FW is ready for a new task.

The complexity of the design was mitigated by designing for debugging using PetaLinux IDE based interactive software debugger (over Ethernet or Serial), and Xilinx XSDK/Vitis SDK interactive debugging (over JTAG). In addition, the design includes a menu-based ground system (GSE) mode for testing; debug mode builds; test cases (production testing, hammer testing and application testing); and FPGA debugging with ILA insertion. Finally, for the Zynq PL, JPL used an ARM AXI/OCP BFM to quickly write (and run) write/read based testcases developed by Alpha Data and Correct Designs. The testcases utilized an enhanced VHDL environment using OSVVM library components and migrated from Xsim to Questa, added Vivado Tcl scripts to automatically build and run regressions from the command line using a configurable, automated regression environment.

4.3 FLEX Testing

Fig. 14 shows the host that drives the PCPS Command and Telemetry UART inputs of the FPIE-D SoC which is running the embedded Flight Software that interprets and executes the commands as defined on the table on the right.

Figure 14. Testing environment of FLEX on FPIE-D SoC

In this configuration, sending commands such as “Start compression” or “Download” data are slow and take time. The GSE Ethernet port on the FPIE-D SoC is used to upload raw input data and download output compressed data which are checked with the output of a software-based version of the compressor (reference model).

This environment was used to write tests at higher, abstract level, using simple python scripts to interact with the FPIE-D SoC. We developed a small library of python tests, that use a Host Software SerialRemote python API that mimics the commands supported by the FPIE-D SoC. The SerialRemote code running on the host, is actually library that shared with the code compiled into the FPIE-D SoC. The host Python and SerialRemote code are used to validate the design as part of a nightly build and test flow controlled by Jenkins. It gives us a nice way to automate our daily testing of new builds on hardware. We run smaller versions of similar tests in simulation, but those tests do not exercise the Flight Software or any hardware directly. The simulation tests just exercise the FLEX RTL using a bus functional model in place of the ARM core & SW but do feed the compressor with specific set of data patterns to prove the cores compress correctly.

5 FPIE-D FPGA KU060 BASED HARDWARE PLATFORM FOR GROUND TESTING

5.1 Hardware Description

Zynq is not a space grade part, so we decided to port the data compression block to a space grade KU060 part on the Alpha Data ADM-XRC-KU1 board (Fig. 15) [15].

Figure 15. KU060 FPGA Hardware architecture for FLEX lossless and lossy Data Compression testing

For the testing of the FLEX BIL in lossless and lossy configuration we used a hardware development platform which consists of an Ubuntu linux computer with a Alpha Data ADM-XRC-KU1. The ADM-XRC-KU1 board is a mezzanine card integrated in Alpha Data ADC-PCIe-XMC carrier board plug-in in PC through PCI express interface. The board has four 2GBytes DDR4 SDRAM with a data throughput of 19.2 Gbytes/sec per bank. It communicates through the host through PCI express Gen2 x4 with a data throughput of 1.4 Gbytes/sec. This is much faster path than sending commands and data to an FPIE-D SoC system through its serial interfaces and ethernet enabling much greater throughput in our pseudo random test environment. The software running on the host is generating the random image data, generating Random Data Initialization, compute the expected compressed data using FLEX single core Software and compare expected and firmware results.

5.2 Software and Firmware architecture

The Software/FPGA Multi core Data compression architecture consists of 3 elements (Fig. 16). The first element is the “FLEX application software” which decomposes the images into a set of segments made of 32 images which are passed on to the FLEX API Software layer. The second element is the “FLEX API Software and FPGA Interface Abstraction” which handles configuration and the interaction with FPGA card. It consists of a “scheduler” which queue the segment and manage a set of workers assigned a FLEX IP Core. The “worker” handles the data transfer to the FPGA SDRAM, then triggers the FLEX core to execute and acquire the compress data. Finally the 3rd element is the “FLEX FPGA Design” which compresses up to 11 segments in parallel. In this architecture each FLEX IP Core works independently on the data stored in the SDRAM banks attached to the FPGA, uploads and downloads intermediary data to and from its own FPGA SDRAM partition, and finally Downloads compressed data in FPGA SDRAM and alerts its FLEX worker that the job is done.

5.3 FLEX Testing

A set of scripts and software to stress test the JPL FLEX firmware cores were developed and packaged in a GitHub module called ‘flex_bil_tester’. The code is used to generate pseudo random hyperspectral images which are compressed with a Software Codec to proceed the expected compression output.

Figure 17. FLEX testing Architecture on KU060

The same raw input images are fed to the FPIE-D FPGA board and the resulting compression output is compared against the software codec output (GOLDEN MODEL) to ensure the HW is operating correctly. The scripts generate, run and compare patterns non-stop, deleting all the data for passing tests and saving failing testcases. At the same time, the seed of ALL tests saved so any test can be re-generated and re-run at any time. The generator has a lot of knobs that control the pseudo random raw compression input (dimensions, entropy, lossyness, etc).

The console on the right of Fig. 17 shows how the random generator and runner are used to bias towards specific scenarios. In addition, it shows how the script logs testcase results as jobs are run. We have additional analysis scripts in the package that track how many tests we’ve run, what dimensions were exercises, pass/fail results, etc.. The Hammer test (final run on the released hardware) of the FLEX consists of

- Image pattern: Random change of least significant bit
- Image size: cross-track between 32 and 1280 by increment of 32 and band between 32 and 480 by increment of 8
- Lossyness parameters: Random lossyness per band from 0 (lossless) to 1023 (max_error on sample)
- Over 20,052,424 images with different size or 23 TB of data (for comparison, EMIT from 08/01/2022 to 09/18/2023: 47.5 TB)

5.4 Performance

Alpha Data provides software that measures the time it takes each thread within the KU60 compression job to complete, allowing us to plot compression performance for various FLEX cores and input compression jobs. The activities of the workers and their associated cores are analysed using Alpha Data Tools collecting real-time information when performing the data compression. The graph on the left on Fig. 18 shows the state of the workers and the associated core in function of time. Each horizontal bar represents a worker. There are 11 workers, one for each core, as shown in the red rectangle. The graph shows that the upload of raw data, the compression and the download operation are pipeline. Due to the fast download and upload, after uploading the data in the DDR, the worker is stalled waiting for its FLEX core to finish compressing. The graph on the top left of Fig. 18 shows the DMA transfer from the CPU to the FPGA DDR during the compression of 256 segments over 11 cores. We can see that we reach some time the limit of PCIe of 1.4GBytes/sec. The graph on the bottom of Fig. 18 shows the data transfer between the FPGA and the DDR4 during upload/download and data compression. It reaches 3.6 GBytes/sec which is much less that the DDR maximum data bandwidth of 18 Gbytes/sec. In conclusion, the pipelining of the upload of raw data, compression of the raw data and the download of the compressed data by the software/FPGA architecture allows the compress data to be independent of the time required to upload or download of the data. In addition, the limited PCIe data bandwidth (1.4 GBytes/sec) has no effect on the compression

data throughput. Finally, in a flight implementation, the Software/FPGA architecture allows the space craft host processor to perform real-time data acquisition and data downlink while simultaneously FPGA performs real-time data compression

Figure 18. FLEX Performance on Alpha Data ADM-XRC-KU1 board

6 COMPRESSION DATA THROUGHPUT

We analysed the data throughput performance for multiple JPL systems with FLEX IP Cores. The graph in Fig. 19 shows the data throughput for each system along with the the number of cores and the image size processed. The analysis considers two implementations of the FLEX: (1) one following the CCSDS standard (FLEX BIP) (2) one with has a slight modification of CCSDS to allow pipeline inside the compression core, resulting in a 2.5x increase in data throughput while preserving the data compression ratio. The analysis also considers the number of cores: (1) 3 cores used by EMIT FPIE-D SoC on Zynq 7z100 and FPIE-D SoC on Zynq 7z045 both maximizing the resource utilization of the Zynq PL (2) 11 cores (for FLEX BIL) maximizing the resource available of KU060. Finally, the analysis considers the image size to take full advantage of the pipeline capabilities providing the maximum data throughput of the compression IP independently of upload or download of data. The FPGA resource utilization of the FLEX BIL 11 cores on the KU060 is shown in Fig. 20. The software and FPGA architecture using a KU060 can achieve up to a 218 MSamples/sec compression data throughput. This performance enables real-time data compression for current mission such as EMIT FPIE-D SoC 7z100 (45 MSamples/sec) and FPIE-D SoC 7z045 (40 MSamples/sec) and for future missions with larger focal plane detectors and multiple imagers operating in parallel. This performance allows also to dedicate the FLEX implementation to the FPGA firmware and relieve the CPU to run other essential tasks.

Figure 19. Data Throughput of FLEX on FPIE-D FPGA (KU060) and SoC (Zynq)

Site Type	Used	Available	Utilization %
CLB LUTs	300567	331680	90.62
CLB Registers	309541	663360	46.66
Block RAM	711.5	1080	65.88
DSP	650	2760	23.55

Figure 20: Resource utilization of the FLEX BIL 11 cores on the FPIE-D FPGA KU060

7 CONCLUSION

The FLEX BIL data compression block (a modified implementation of the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 standard), modified compared to the implementation of FLEX BIP used by the EMIT mission, was implemented as FPIE-D AMD SoC Zynq-based and FPIE-D FPGA KU060-based versions using respectively Alpha Data COTS ADM-XRC-7z1 assembly and Alpha Data COTS KU1 PCIe board. The BIL firmware and algorithm enhancements provided an increase in data throughput by a factor of 2.5 compared to the EMIT FLEX implementation, achieving a data throughput of 218 MSamples/sec using an 11 FLEX BIL core implementation on an Alpha Data COTS KU1 board. The next development will consist of implementing the FLEX software/hardware architecture presented in this paper on AMD Versal ACAP VC1902 AI Core Device using the Alpha Data COTS ADM-PA100 board to provide a space grade implementation with increased capacity for even more FLEX cores and the option of utilizing AI engines and other enhancements available in the Versal SoC.

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REFERENCES

- [1] EMIT Web site: <https://earth.jpl.nasa.gov/emit/>
- [2] Green, Robert O., Natalie Mahowald, Charlene Ung, David R. Thompson, Lori Bator, Matthew Bennet, Michael Bernas et al. "The Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation: An Earth Science Imaging Spectroscopy Mission.", in IEEE Aerospace 2020.
- [3] Committee on the Decadal Survey for Earth Science and Applications from Space, Space Studies Board, "Thriving on Our Changing Planet: A Decadal Strategy for Earth Observation from Space", The National Academies Press, 2018.
- [4] D. Keymeulen, H. Luong, T. Pham, A. Kiely, M. Klimesh, M. Cheng, D. Dolman, C. Holyoake, K. Crocker, "Hardware implementation of Lossless and Lossy Compression of Space-based Multispectral and Hyperspectral Imagery," in Proceedings of 2016 HyspIRI Science and Applications Workshop, 18 - 20 October 2016, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA.
- [5] Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS), Lossless Data Compression, Recommendation for space data system standards vol. 121.0-B-1: CCSDS, 1997. (<http://public.ccsds.org>)
- [6] C. Hartzell, L. Graham, T. Tao, H. Goldberg, J. Carpena-Nunez, D. Racek, C. Taylor, C. Norton, "Data System Design for a Hyperspectral Imaging Mission Concept," in Proceedings of IEEE Aerospace Conference 2009.
- [7] E. Blem, J. Menon, and K. Sankaralingam, Detailed Analysis of Contemporary ARM and x86 Architectures, Technical report, University of Wisconsin - Madison, 2013.
- [8] N. Mehta, Xilinx 7 Series FPGAs: The Logical Advantage, Xilinx WP405, 2012.

- [9] Zynq-7000 SoC Technical Reference Manual Xilinx: https://www.xilinx.com/support/documentation/user_guides/ug585-Zynq-7000-TRM.pdf (UG585 (v1.13), April 2, 2021)
- [10] Longlei Li, Natalie M. Mahowald, Yves Balkanski, Paul Ginoux, Maria Goncalves Ageitos, Robert O. Green, Douglas S. Hamilton, Olga Kalashnikova, Martina Klose, Jasper F. Kok, Ron L. Miller, Vincenzo Obiso, David Paynter, Carlos Perez Garcia-Pando, David R. Thompson, “Quantifying the range of the dust direct radiative effect due to source mineralogy uncertainty”, In *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 21, 3973-4005, 2021.
- [11] Bogdan V. Oaida, Amruta Yelamanchili, Christopher Wells, David R. Thompson, Robert O. Green, Matthew W. Bennett, Didier Keymeulen, Thang Pham, Daniel P. Poe, Lena Siskind, Charlene Ung, “Mapping Earth’s Dust-Emitting Regions from the ISS with the EMIT Imaging Spectrometer” in *IEEE Aerospace 2022*
- [12] Low-complexity lossless and near-lossless multispectral and hyperspectral image compression. Report Concerning Space Data System Standards, CCSDS 123.0-B-2. Blue Book. Washington, D.C.: CCSDS, February 2019 [Online] (<https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/123x0b2c3.pdf>) Green Book. Washington, D.C.: CCSDS, December 2022 [Online] (<https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/120x2g2.pdf>)
- [13] Alpha Data ADM-XRC-7z1 high performance reconfigurable XMC (compliant to VITA 42.0) based on the Xilinx Zynq range of Programmable System-on-Chips, <https://www.alpha-data.com/product/adm-xrc-7z1/>
- [14] Alpha Data ADM-XRC-KU1 high performance reconfigurable XMC (compliant to VITA Standard 42.0 and 42.3) based on the AMD Kintex Ultrascale range of Platform FPGAs, <https://www.alpha-data.com/product/adm-xrc-ku1/>
- [15] D. Keymeulen et al. “Data Compression and Cloud Screening using a High-Performance Embedded System-on-a-Chip for the Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation (EMIT) imaging spectrometer on the International Space Station (ISS)” In *Proceedings of 8th International Workshop on on-board payload data compression (OBPDC-2022)*, Athens, Greece, 28-30 September, 2022.
- [16] M. Hernandez et al. “The CCSDS 123.0-B-2 “Low-Complexity Lossless and Near-Lossless Multispectral and Hyperspectral Image Compression” Standard. In *Journal of IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, December 2021.
- [17] A. Sanchez et al. “Reducing Data Dependencies in the Feedback Loop of the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 Predictor”. In *Journal of IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters* Vol. 19, 2022.
- [18] D. Valsesia et al. “High-Throughput Onboard Hyperspectral Image Compression With Ground-Based CNN Reconstruction”. In *Journal of IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, Vol. 57 No. 12 December 2019.
- [19] D. Bascones et al. “A Real-Time FPGA Implementation of the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 Standard” In *Journal of IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, Vol. 60, April 12, 2022.
- [20] P. Chatziantoniou et al. “An Efficient Architecture and High-Throughput Implementation of CCSDS-123.0-B-2 Hybrid Entropy Coder Targeting Space-Grade SRAM FPGA Technology”. In *Journal of IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electric Systems*, Vol 59, No. 6, 6 December 2022.
- [21] P. Chatziantoniou et al. “A Parallel Architecture and Implementation for Near-Lossless Hyperspectral Image Compression Based on CCSDS 123.0-B-2 With Scalable Data-Rate Performance” In *Journal of IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, Vol 32, pp 161-1629, September, 2024.
- [22] D. Keymeulen et al. “High-Performance Embedded Space Computing System-on-Chip for space imaging spectrometer” in *Proceedings of IEEE Space Mission Challenges for Information Technology - IEEE Space Computing Conference (IEEE SMC-IT/SCC 2023)* Caltech, Pasadena, July 18-21, 2023.
- [23] D. Keymeulen et al. “High-Performance Embedded System-on-a-Chip for space imaging spectrometer” In *Proceedings of IEEE Aerospace Conference Big Sky*, MT, USA, March 5-10, 2023.